

Phytochemical studies and antioxidant activity of crude extract of *Oenanthe javanica* blume DC.

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the qualitative and quantitative phytochemical composition and antioxidant activity of a methanolic extract from the whole plant. Qualitative analysis revealed a rich diversity of compounds, including tannins, alkaloids, phenols, steroids, and flavonoids. Quantitatively, the extract was characterized by a significant tannin content of 0.43 mg/g AE/g and a total alkaloid content of 0.29 mg/g GAE, highlighting its potential as an antioxidant source. Antioxidant activity was evaluated using the Ferric Reducing Antioxidant Power (FRAP) assay and the Superoxide Scavenging (SO) assay. The FRAP assay showed the highest Radical Scavenging Activity (RSA) at 133.27%, surpassing the standard ascorbic acid (AA), which had an RSA of 72.38%. This result underscores the extracts strong capability to neutralize free radicals and reduce oxidative stress. Additionally, the extract demonstrated an IC₅₀ value in the range of 50-200 µg/ml, indicating an effective concentration for inhibiting 50% of free radicals. These findings suggest that the methanolic whole plant extract possesses significant antioxidant properties, likely due to its diverse phytochemical composition. Such antioxidant-rich extracts hold potential for applications in health and nutrition, especially in combating oxidative stress-related disorders. The study highlights the promising role of this plant extract in promoting health and mitigating oxidative damage.

Keywords: *Oenanthe javanica*, Phytochemistry, Quantitative, FRAP, SO

INTRODUCTION

Before modern drugs began to take shape in the medical care industry, people were highly dependent on conventional or traditional medicine, which have been recognized by the World Health Organization as reliable medicinal sources for therapeutic activities [1]. Medicinal plants, the “backbone” of traditional medicine, are utilized today by more than 3.3 billion people in the less developed countries [2].

Oenanthe javanica (Blume) DC is an aquatic perennial herb belonging to the family Apiaceae. East Asian nations such China, Japan, Korea, Thailand, Malaysia, and Australia are the primary places where it is grown [3]. Water dropwort exhibits therapeutic effects and has a high mineral and vitamin content [3], [4]. In China, it has long been consumed as a vegetable. According to several studies, *O. javanica* contains three significant components: persicarin, isorhamnetin, and hypero side. These compounds have been shown to have pharmacological actions that can be used to treat a variety of illnesses [3]. The control of free radicals quenching pathway with the antioxidant defense in the context of water dropwort's salt tolerance mechanism is mostly unknown.

Many pharmacological actions of *O. Javanica* have been documented, such as hepatoprotective [5, 6], antiviral [11], immunological enhancing ethanol elimination [9], antioxidant [10], and anti-inflammatory [7, 8]. *O. javanica* has been shown to contain coumarins [12], flavonoids and flavonoid glycosides [13], and polyphenols [14] according to phytochemical analyses. Furthermore, toxicity tests have shown that *O. javanica* does not show any genetic or acute toxicity [13], [14]. On the other hand, at high doses, oral delivery of dry *O. Javanica* powder may cause a significant loss in weight and food consumption in mice and increase the rate of sperm malformation [13]. Furthermore, a reversible subchronic toxicity was demonstrated by a total phenolic acid extract from *O. javanica* at a high dose (20 times the approved human clinical dose). The study goals were to assess the crude plant extract of *Oenanthe javanica* Blume (DC.) based on qualitative phytochemical analysis. to ascertain the tannin and total alkaloid levels. to investigate the crude plant extract antioxidant properties utilizing two distinct techniques: super oxide radical scavenging (SO) and ferric reducing antioxidant power (FRAP).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Oenanthe Javanica Blume DC, whole plant were collected from Laphupat Tera Bishnupur District Manipur, India 28-03-2023 and used for the present investigation. The taxonomic authenticity of the above plant was identified by Dr. D. Kumarasamy, renowned taxonomist, Annamalai University. The collected plants materials were surface sterilized with 1% mercuric chloride and thoroughly washed with plenty of distilled water [16]. The plant material was dried under shade with occasional shifting. Later, the dried plants were chopped into small piece and stored in an airtight container. Methanol solvent was used in extraction procedure.

Qualitative Phytochemical analysis

The crude plant extracts of *Oenanthe javanica* in methanol were qualitatively analyzed for the identification of secondary metabolites viz., alkaloids, flavonoids, glycosides, phenols, saponins, steroids, terpenoids and tannins by using standard protocols. Phytochemical screenings were carried out for the selected extracts as per the standard methods [17], [18].

Quantitative phytochemical analysis

Determination of Total Alkaloid Content (TAC) [19]

The amount of alkaloids in total was stated as milligrams of AE per gram of extract. One milliliter of the plant extract was denatured in DMSO before one milliliter of 2N HCL was added and filtered. This mixture was moved into a separating funnel, where it was combined with 5 milliliters of phosphate buffer and 5 milliliters of bromocresol green solution. The mixture was vigorously shaken with 1, 2, 3, and 4 ml of chloroform before being collected in a 10 ml volumetric flask and diluted to the appropriate volume with chloroform. The mixture absorbance was calculated at 470 nm.

Determination of Total Tannin Content [19]

Plant extract's total tannin content was determined using the Folin-Ciocalteu method. 0.5 ml of Folin reagent was added to the mixture after about 0.1 ml of plant extract had been dissolved in 7.5 ml of distilled water. With distilled water, dilute 1 ml of 35% Na₂CO₃ to 10 ml. After giving the mixture a good shake, it was left at room temperature for half an hour. Gallic acid reference standard solutions were made with concentrations of 20, 40, 60, 80, and 100 µg/ml. Using a UV/Visible spectrophotometer, the absorbance of the test and standard

solutions was measured at 725 nm in relation to the blank. The amount of tannin in each milligram of GAE per gram of extract was stated.

Non-Enzymatic Antioxidant assays

1. FRAP Assay (Ferric Reduced Antioxidant Potential): This method was followed according to Benzie and strain method [20].

Determination of FRAP method

After 30 minutes at 37°C, 3 milliliters of the produced FRAP reagent is combined with varying quantities of standard ascorbic acid (50, 100, 150, and 200µl) at concentration that range from 10 to 100µg/ml. The absorbance at 593 nm is then recorded. By contrasting the absorption change in the test mixture with those obtained from increasing the quantity of ascorbic acid equivalents moles/ml or FRAP units, FRAP values can be determined. As positive controls, butylated hydroxy toluene and ascorbic acid were employed. Expressed as mg of GAE per g of extract.

2. Super Oxide radical scavenging activity

Add 0.1 ml of extract of different concentrations (20, 40, 60, 80, and 100µg) and of 50, 100, 150, and 200µg to 0.1 ml of Nitroblueterazolium (156 Mm), 1 ml of Nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide (reduced) (468 µm), and 0.1 mL of Phenanzine methosulphate solution (PMS) in 0.1 M of phosphate buffer solution (pH 7.4). After 5 minutes of incubation at 25°C, absorbance was measured at 560 nm against blank containing all reagents except PMS. Standard dosage of ascorbic acid was used [21]. The super oxide radical scavenging activity was computed using the subsequent formula.

$$\text{Superoxide Radical scavenged (\%)} = [1 - A_t/A_o \times 100]$$

Where it is the absorbance of the sample and A_o is the absorbance of the control at 560 nm.

Statistical Analysis

The triplicates of data obtained from the experimental study were subjected to statistical analysis. Mean and standard deviation were calculated using SPSS-(DMRT) Duncan's Multiple Range test.

RESULT

Qualitative Phytochemical Analysis

Appropriate phytochemical tests were employed to investigate the phytochemical constituents present in the crude extract of *Oenanthe javanica*. (Table1) The preliminary phytochemical analysis of ten different secondary metabolites were performed in methanol extracts of *Oenanthe javanica*. Seven tests conferred positive results and remaining ten gave negative result. The plant species showed significant indication about the presence of various bioactive secondary metabolites viz., alkaloids, phenol, flavonoids, steroids and tannins.

Table 1: Preliminary Qualitative Phytochemical Analysis of *Oenanthe javanica*.

Sl. No.	Secondary metabolites	Tests Performed	Observation	Result
1	Saponin	Foam test	Foam persists more than 10 minutes	-
		Froth test	Persistent foam	-
2	Tannin	1% HCl test	Formation of red precipitate	+
3	Alkaloid	Mayer's test	Buff colored precipitate appears	++
		Wagner's test	Formation of red precipitate appears	+
4	Phenol	Ellagic test	Chocolate brown color appears	+
5	Phlobatannin	1% HCl test	No formation of red precipitate	-
6	Steroids	Salkowski's test	formation of reddish-brown color	+
		Lieberman-Burchard's test	Color development from violet to blue	+
		Keller-Killiani test	No appearance of reddish-brown ring	-
7	Terpenoids	Glacial acetic test	No pink to violet color formation	-
8	Glycosides	Conc. H ₂ SO ₄ test	No formation of red color	-
		Keller-Killiani test	No formation of reddish-brown ring	-
9	Anthraquinone	Borntrager's test	No appearance of pink, red or violet color	-
10	Flavonoids	1% ammonia test	Appearance of yellow color	+
		Shinoda test	No Appearance of red color	-
		Lead-acetate test	No Appearance of buff color	-

Quantitative Phytochemical Analysis

Total Alkaloid Content

Spectrophotometric analysis was used to determine the total alkaloid content. A higher overall alkaloid content was discovered in methanolic extracts, with 0.43 ± 0.02 mg AE/g. At $100 \mu\text{g/ml}$, the standard curve of an alkaloid (tannic acid) is displayed in Fig. 1. It is possible to deduce that the use of methanol as the solvent has resulted in a more effective extraction of alkaloids as compared to alternative solvents or techniques that could have been employed. The concentration of $100 \mu\text{g/ml}$ indicates that a considerable amount of alkaloids might be extracted from the sample at this particular concentration.

Fig. 1: Graph showing standard curve for total alkaloid content (Quercetin)

Total Tannin Content

Total tannin content in crude methanolic extracts of the plant sample was quantified by Folin - Ciocalteu method. Methanolic whole plant extracts showed 0.29 ± 0.09 mg of GAE/g at $100 \mu\text{g/ml}$ (Fig 2).

In addition, the degree of variability or uncertainty in the measurements is indicated by the variation in the results, as represented by the $\pm$ values. There are several possible reasons for this, such as sample heterogeneity, measurement accuracy, or experimental circumstances.

Fig. 2: Graph showing standard curve for total tannin content (Tannic acid) Antioxidant Activity of *Oenanthe javanica*.

Ferric Reducing Antioxidant Power (FRAP) Assay:

The methanolic whole plant extract had the highest Radical Scavenging Activity (RSA) in the Ferric Reducing Antioxidant Power (FRAP) experiment, measuring 133.29 ± 1.61 . This was in comparison to the standard ascorbic acid, which exhibited an RSA of 172.38 ± 1.39 at a dosage of $200 \mu\text{g/ml}$. The ascorbic acid and whole plant extract IC₅₀ values within the $50\text{-}200 \mu\text{g/ml}$ concentration range were found to be 115.88 ± 1.11 and 90.85 ± 0.98 , respectively. The concentration at which 50% of ferric ions are reduced is represented by these values, which show each extract's potential for antioxidant activity (Fig. 3).

The high percentage of RSA in the FRAP assay indicates that the methanolic extract has significant antioxidant activity, according to the data. This is a significant result since antioxidants are essential for reducing oxidative stress, which is a cause of many diseases.

Also, the notable antioxidant capacity of ascorbic acid, a widely known the norm, bolsters the effectiveness of the examined extracts. All things considered, these results further our knowledge of the antioxidant potential of the methanolic whole plant extract and highlight its possible application in the creation of natural antioxidant-based treatments or supplements targeted at oxidative stress-related illnesses.

Fig. 3: Graph showing the FRAP scavenging activity of methanolic extract of *Oenanthe javanica* whole plant by comparing with Ascorbic acid (Standard).

Superoxide (SO) Assay:

As demonstrated in Figure 4, the methanolic whole plant extract had the highest percentage of Radical Scavenging Activity (RSA) in the Superoxide Scavenging Assay, at 27.16 ± 0.89 . At $200 \mu\text{g/ml}$, the standard ascorbic acid exhibits a percentage of RSA of 55.68 ± 0.49 . In the concentration range of $100\text{--}200 \mu\text{g/ml}$, the IC_{50} values for the ascorbic acid and methanolic plant extract were reported to be 47.61 ± 0.85 and $50.000 \pm 150.200 \mu\text{g/ml}$, respectively.

With lower IC_{50} values indicating better antioxidant capability, these data show each extract's capacity to scavenge superoxide radicals. Despite having a lower RSA than other solvent extracts, the methanolic leaf extract showed a comparatively lower IC_{50} value, demonstrating its effectiveness in neutralizing superoxide radicals at lower doses. Significant superoxide scavenging action was also demonstrated by ordinary ascorbic acid, confirming its well-known antioxidant qualities. Overall, these results shed light on the antioxidant

potential of various solvent extracts made from the plant leaves. The different RSA and IC50 values indicate that the antioxidant capacity of the isolated compounds can be strongly influenced by the solvent selection. These findings further our knowledge of antioxidants natural sources and possible uses against oxidative stress-related conditions.

Fig. 4: Graph showing the SO radical scavenging activity of methanolic extract of *Oenanthe javanica* whole plant by comparing with ascorbic acid (Standard).

DISCUSSION

The majority of the phytoconstituents have been found in the crude methanolic extracts of *O. javanica*, according to phytochemical screening. According to reports, the plant includes chemicals such as phenolic acids, flavonoids, and phenylpropanoids, particularly isorhamnetin and persicarin. To find significant phytochemicals that might be connected to plant extracts antioxidant activity, preliminary phytochemical screening often gets carried out [22], [23], [24].

Total alkaloid and tannin content, as well as total flavonoid content, were found to be greater in the methanolic extract of *O. javanica*, according to Wang *et al.*, (2017) [13]. The most researched category of polyphenol chemicals is flavonoids, which are frequently found conjugated to sugars in plants. The DPPH free radical scavenging experiment results, according to Cho *et al.* (2003) [25], indicate that the entire *O. javanica* plant has strong antioxidant properties. This may be because the extracts contain a variety of phytochemicals, primarily alkaloids. It was discovered that isorhamnetin, which was isolated from the aerial section of *O. javanica*, had robust radical scavenging action. Alkaloid concentration was higher in ethanol extract than in aqueous extract, and it also shown stronger DPPH

scavenging activity and reducing power, according to antioxidant activity and phytochemical studies by Hwang *et al.*, (2011) [26]. Free radical compound DPPH is frequently used to evaluate a sample's capacity to scavenge free radicals [26]. Similar patterns were seen in the reducing power assay and total antioxidant activity of *O. javanica* methanolic and crude alkaloid extracts, showing that as concentration increased, so did reducing power and antioxidant activity. Bioactive components in the extract that have the potential to supply electrons may be essential for some of the extracts reducing power. An important measure of the antioxidant activity of the Fe³⁺ complex is its ability to convert to the ferrous (Fe²⁺) form in the presence of reducers [27]. The existence of *O. javanica* ferric reducing capacity and total phenolic content free radical scavenging was also reported by Chan *et al.* (2016) [28]. Numerous assays, including those that scavenge the 2,2-diphenylpicrylhydrazyl (DPPH) radical, measure oxygen radical absorbance capacity (ORAC), ferric reducing antioxidant power (FRAP), and Xanthine oxidase, have been used to assess *O. javanica* antioxidant activity. The first method used to determine the antioxidant activity of *O. javanica* methanol extract was the FRAP test. Furthermore, at a dosage of 10 mg/ml, the 95% ethanol extract of the dried leaves showed inhibitory effects on SOD activity and radical scavenging for DPPH, with inhibition rates of $56.87 \pm 1.43\%$ and $73.51 \pm 0.54\%$, respectively.

Its phenolic content and antioxidant activity, however, did not significantly correlate. Similarly, the DPPH test was used to determine the antioxidant capabilities of the *O. javanica* methanol extract, and the results indicated that the IC₅₀ value was $87.42 \pm 0.64 \mu\text{g/ml}$. The hydrophilic ORAC and FRAP activities of *O. javanica* were recently demonstrated by Kongkachuichai *et al.*, (2015) [29] to be approximately 9000 and 2000 $\mu\text{mol Trolox equivalent /100 g fresh weight}$, respectively. Studies on *O. javanica* antioxidant activity in relation to phenolics have not yet shown definitive results [30, 31]. observed an increase in DPPH activity in the dark and indicated that this rise was caused by the higher level of polyphenols, ascorbic acid, and alpha-tocopherol. reported an increase in overall antioxidant capacity among five cultivars of blanched water dropwort [32].

CONCLUSION

The research Concluded that the Methanolic Whole Plant Extract of *O. javanica* having phytochemistry like alkaloid, tannin, phenols etc. The plant also having potential of high antioxidant activity. However, the lack of research by local researchers even when the Plant is well known locality should be Changed. Antioxidant activity more than one Method should be done to get more reliable results. These Plant suggested that could be a valuable source of natural compounds for developing new therapeutic drugs in recent years.

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